

Human-robot cooperative grasping of large objects

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Abstract—Human-robot co-grasping allows the collaborative transportation of large objects in industrial and domestic settings and represents an important challenge in the research area of physical Human-Robot Interaction (pHRI). Here we propose a method that allows the co-manipulation of large objects by considering an extended contact patch between the robot end-effector and the object. Pressure and friction constraints are derived from the geometrical properties of the contact area and are at the basis of a control strategy which allows the robot to maintain the grasp stable while following the human motion.

Index Terms—Cooperative grasping, Physical Human-Robot Interaction, Contact modeling

I. INTRODUCTION

Physical human-robot interaction (pHRI) is one of the main challenges the robotic community has faced in the last two decades [1]. A fundamental requirement is that robots, and in particular robot manipulators, should be capable of safely handling unwanted collisions with humans [2]. However, once safety is guaranteed, there is also the possibility of actually exploiting the physical interaction between humans and robots to execute complex tasks. An example is the human-robot cooperative grasping and manipulation of objects that are too heavy and/or too large to be manipulated by a human alone [3]. In this case, the contact has to involve an extended surface. Up to now, however, in the theory of grasping only little attention has been put on explicitly accounting for the properties of the contacting surface in the contact modelling.

Here, we present a method suitable for human-robot co-manipulative tasks, where the robot does not tightly grasp the object through a gripper, but contacts the object through an extended patch, as if it was an additional finger (see Fig. 1). By means of this extended contact, forces and torques can be applied in all directions, differently from what is assumed in classical contact models that consider contact *points* and not *areas* [4]. As a result, the grasp is more reliable and a full control over the object pose is possible. As described in detail in our recent work [5], to properly model the extended contact patch, the geometric properties of the surface need to be considered to derive pressure constraints and friction limits. Next sections describe the proposed *Extended Patch model* and how this can be exploited to design a robot control scheme for effective human-robot collaborative grasping of large objects.

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Fig. 1. Cooperative grasp between a human and a robot. The human guides the cooperative manipulation task and the robot ensure the grasp maintenance.

II. THE EXTENDED PATCH MODEL

For the sake of simplicity, let us assume that the contact surface is flat and made of linear elastic material, as if an elastic plate was located at the robot end-effector (Fig. 1). When the plate contacts the object, it applies an equivalent contact wrench λ_c at the center of the contact patch C . λ_c collects the contact forces \mathbf{f}_c and moments \mathbf{m}_c in C : $\lambda_c = [\mathbf{f}_c^T, \mathbf{m}_c^T]^T$, and is balanced by the resultant of the tangential stresses and normal pressures applied to the plate. In each infinitesimal area dS of the contact patch there are a normal pressure $p(x, y)$ and two tangential stress components τ_x and τ_y . The resultant force and moment related to p , τ_x and τ_y , that have to balance λ_c , are:

$$f_{cx} = - \int_S \tau_x dS, \quad f_{cy} = - \int_S \tau_y dS, \quad f_{cz} = - \int_S p dS \quad (1)$$

$$m_{cx} = - \int_S p y dS, \quad m_{cy} = \int_S p x dS, \quad m_{cz} = - \int_S (-\tau_x y + \tau_y x) dS \quad (2)$$

From our hypotheses, it follows that the pressure distribution must be linear in x and y : $p = p_0 + ax + by$, otherwise, the contact would be lost after the deformation. Parameters p_0 , a and b depend on the contact wrench λ_c and the plate surface S , and can be retrieved by carrying out the computations in Eq. (1) and Eq. (2) involving p . If we assume that the surface of the plate is rectangular (sides l_1 and l_2), it comes out:

$$p = \frac{f_{cz}}{l_1 l_2} + \frac{3m_{cy}}{l_1^3 l_2} x + \frac{3m_{cx}}{l_1 l_2^3} y. \quad (3)$$

Eq. (3) shows that the pressure is the sum of three terms: the first one is the mean pressure, due to the application of a normal force on a surface, while the others are the contributions provided by the applied torques in x and y directions. In order for the flat contact to hold, $p(x, y) > 0$ must be satisfied for any point on the plate.

III. ROBOT CONTROL

To investigate the role played by the pressure constraints, we compared two different control schemes, namely the Extended Patch (EP) method and the Single Point (SP) method. In SP, the robot is controlled so that: *a*) the normal component of the contact force f_n is bounded between two limits f_{min} and f_{max} ; *b*) the contact force \mathbf{f}_c is inside the Coulomb's friction cone. The violation of these constraints generates a force compensation term: $\mathbf{e}_f = \mathbf{e}_n + \mathbf{e}_t$, where \mathbf{e}_n is evaluated to assure that $f_{min} < f_n < f_{max}$, while \mathbf{e}_t keeps f_t within Coulomb's friction limits. The contact moment component, \mathbf{e}_m , is an action opposite to \mathbf{m}_c and is applied to keep its value as low as possible, i.e. $\mathbf{e}_m = -\mathbf{m}_c$.

Concerning the EP method, the main difference with respect to the SP control lies in the evaluation of $\mathbf{e}_m = [e_{mx}, e_{my}, e_{mz}]$, that here explicitly takes into account the previously introduced contact properties and limits. e_{mz} action is applied if the normal component of contact moment exceeds torsional friction limits, i.e. if $m_{cz} > \mu_t f_{cz}$, and e_{mx} and e_{my} actions are applied if the equivalent pressure distribution $p(x, y) < 0$ in some parts of the contact patch. More specifically, let us denote with p_{min} the minimum value of the pressure at the plate corners. If $p_{min} < 0$, a corrective term $\mathbf{e}_{mb} = [e_{mx}, e_{my}, 0]$, is evaluated as $\mathbf{e}_{mb} = -k_{mb}|p_{min}|\mathbf{b}$. Its magnitude is proportional to $|p_{min}|$, and its direction is opposite to the tangential component of the contact moment, whose direction is defined by unit vector \mathbf{b} .

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND DISCUSSION

To investigate the EP contact model, experiments with a 7 DoFs collaborative robotic arm were performed. *Characterization* experiments were aimed at evaluating the precision and overall functioning of the proposed EP and SP control strategies, while *Pick-and-Place* experiments were aimed at analysing users' behaviour during a representative task suitable for industrial and domestic settings.

In *Characterization* experiments, an expert operator was asked to move a box in cooperation with the robot, performing a simple trajectory of 50 cm along only one axis (x , y or z), while keeping as constant as possible the Cartesian coordinates not explicitly involved in the task execution. To have insights on how much the Cartesian coordinates are perturbed during the task execution, the difference between the initial and the final positions was recorded for each trial and the standard deviations along each direction of motion were computed. Experiments revealed that the EP method allows to control well all coordinates (with a maximum deviation of about 2 cm), while human performance is less satisfactory with the SP approach (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Left: example of Characterization experiments. Right: the SP method allows less contact permanence than the EP method.

In *Pick-and-Place* experiments (setup shown in Fig. 1), a naive operator is asked to translate and rotate a box from a start position to a target position. Task completion time, and average norms of the linear velocity and force were recorded. Data analysis revealed that while forces and velocities are similar for both methods, the average completion time decreases by 16% for the EP. Besides that, an interesting consideration can be done on the contact permanence between the plate and the grasped object. For the SP method, at the end of the experiments, an average angle of 30.1° about the plate y -axis appeared between the box and the plate. A much smaller detachment was measured with the EP method (4.3° about the y -axis, 11.4° about the x -axis, see Fig. 2). This implies that in the Single Point method, the operator has to choose whether to reduce the detachment actively (thus finishing the task with the box in a final wrong position), or to accomplish the task precisely (risking to lose the object). This would be particularly disadvantageous if the aid of the robot is necessary not only to stabilize the grasp but also to hold part of the weight of the object.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We presented a novel method to control a robot during a human-robot co-manipulative task where the contact patch between robot and grasped object is large. The proposed approach is based on the geometric modeling of the contact patch and, when compared to a baseline method, it gives better results in terms of trajectory tracking and completion time.

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